

EARTH SCIENCES

DEVELOPMENT OF THE PIMIENTA SHALE FORMATION –THE KEY TO THE GROWTH OF DAILY OIL PRODUCTION IN MEXICO

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Abstract

Since 2005, Mexico has seen a steady decline of daily oil production. Recent offshore oil production projects of the northern part of the Gulf of Mexico had a limited impact on the production decline, which decreased from 3.4 to 1.7 MMbpd. The launch of new offshore fields such as Zama will increase production by no more than 0.1 MMbpd and generally will not change the downward trend of production in Mexico. The solution to this problem is possible through the start of development of the Pimienta shale formation in the Tampico-Misantla and Veracruz oil and gas basins, which will increase daily oil production in Mexico by 0.5-1.5 MMbpd starting in 2030. The potential of the Pimienta formation in the these basins is estimated at 280-560 BBBl of oil, and with an extraction rate of 4-7%, accumulated production may reach 15-45 BBBl. When developing the productive intervals of the Pimienta formation, it is proposed to use the method of cyclic shale development with repeated fracturing, which will extend the life of wells, and, consequently, maintain production at a high level without drilling new production wells.

Keywords: Hydrocarbons (HC), Pimienta formation, Eagle Ford formation, hypercatagenesis, HC shales, zones of HC generation, kitchen rocks, reservoir, cyclic shale development, oil production, Tampico-Misantla basin.

Since 2005, Mexico has seen a decrease of daily production of liquid hydrocarbons (Fig.1) after a sharp drop of oil production in 2007 at the largest Cantarell oil field located in the Campeche Bay. The launch of new offshore fields such as Zama will increase production by no more than 0.1 MMbpd and generally will not

change the downward trend of production in Mexico. The solution to this problem is possible through the start of development of the Pimienta shale formation in the Tampico-Misantla and Veracruz oil and gas basins, which will increase daily oil production in Mexico by 0.5-1.5 MMbpd starting with 2030.

Fig. 1. Daily oil production in Mexico since 1995 to the present (by EIA, CNH and CONACYT).

The reforms currently being implemented by the Mexican government in the oil and gas sector are aimed at attracting investors to work with existing fields with a long history of development and for development of a completely new way of the Mexican Upstream (along with the deep-water offshore of the Gulf of Mexico) - the development of the Pimienta shale formation.

The successful development and accumulated positive experience in the development of gas, condensate and oil deposits in shale formations of the southern United States are certainly a driver of the growth of researches to assess the availability of similar HC resources in the Mexico. Shale formations are widespread in its northern boundary zone [1], where the Upper Cre-

taceous Eagle Ford formation extends into Mexican territory (Agua Nueva formation) in the Sabinas and Burro-Picachos basins. In the central coastal part of Mexico, the Pimienta formation is widespread in the Tampico-Misantla and Veracruz basins, which exceeds the Eagle Ford/Agua Nueva formation by 2-3 times in total thickness (Fig. 2-3).

The Pimienta formation is the main oil and gas source-rock formation of eastern Mexico for all hydrocarbon deposits in the overlying sediments (Eocene, Oligocene, Miocene, Albian, Cenomanian, Upper Jurassic) in traditional reservoirs and traps in the territory of Tampico-Misantla and Veracruz oil and gas basins (Fig. 4)

Fig.2. The regional correlation scheme of shale formations in Mexico [8] (Basins: 1- Chihuahua, 2-Sabinas, 3- Burro-Picachos, 4- Burgos, 5- Tampico-Misantla Misantla, 6- Veracruz).

Fig.3. Gross thickness of Pimienta formation in Tampico-Misantla u Veracruz basins [7].

Fig.4. Oil-and-gas basins of Eastern Mexico where the Pimienta formation is widespread (Source: Advanced Resources International Inc., 2013).

However, the real potential of the Pimienta formation has not been sufficiently studied to date. In 2010-2019, only 25 wells were drilled in the Pimienta formation, and only 5 of them were horizontal wells with multi-stage fracturing in the Tampico-Misantla

province, which showed average starting flow rates of about 900 bpd. The maximum oil flow rate was obtained in the Kaneni-1EXP well at the level of 1932 bpd, where 17 fracturing stages were performed

Fig. 5.

The depth (A) and the catagenesis zonation (B) of the Pimienta formation [7], indicating the direction of thermal and geodynamic effects from the Sierra Madre mountain system on the HC generation and accumulation.

According to the drilling data for Pimienta formation within the western part of the Tampico basin, an abnormally high temperature gradient and abnormally high reservoir pressures were established in the Tithonian sediments of the Pimienta formation due to thermal effects from the Sierra Madre mountain system [7]. The high level of standing of the viscoplastic magmatic hearth here and its convective movement eastward caused extreme heating and accelerated catagenesis (hypercatagenesis) of organomineral substances (OM) in the Pimienta formation in the contact zone from a depth of 500 m from the MK₅ stage (the main gas formation zone), bypassing the stages of protokatagenesis (PK₁₋₃), initial and middle mesokatagenesis (MK₁₋₄) and the main zone of oil generation (MK₁-MK₂) (Fig. 5-6). Approximately along the coastline of the Gulf of Mexico, the boundary between the main zone of condensate generation and the main zone of oil generation passes and the Pimienta formation begins to sink towards the sea aquatory and transition to the generally

accepted regional scheme of OM catagenesis with a normal temperature gradient [2, 3, 5]

The current scheme of the zonation of the HC generation and accumulation in the Pimienta formation in Tampico province was compiled [2] based on deep drilling data, which is confirmed by the results of fracturing in five wells, with the exception of the interval of light oil (MK₂-MK₃). The Horcones-8127 and Furbero-4354 wells produced light oil with a density of 37-38 API and, accordingly, the light oil boundary will shift to the east and run along the coastline of the Gulf of Mexico (fig. 5). The contours of the main zone of condensate generation and main zone of oil generation are confirmed by the drilling results of Pankiwi-1 (49 API) and Kaneni-1 (39 API) wells. Thus, light oil with a density of 37-40 API should be expected in producing wells within central part of Tampico Province, whereas dry gas and condensate should be expected in the western part, in the area adjacent to the Sierra Madre mountain system (Fig. 5-6)

Fig. 6. A seismicogeological section through Tampico province [7] with the release of compressive stresses, abnormal thermal effects, and HC zonation of the Pimienta formation

For potential investors and operating companies, the issue of selecting analogues of shale formations already under development in the North American region that are close to the Pimienta formation in terms of geological, thermobaric, geochemical, and geomechanical characteristics is relevant.

The shale deposits of the Eagle Ford formation in South Texas (USA), where large shale oil, gas and condensate fields have been discovered and are being developed by El Paso, Anadarko, EOG, Petrohawk, Pioneer and others, can be considered as the closest analogue. The first production well for the Eagle Ford formation was drilled by Petrohawk in 2008, and tens of thousands of wells have been drilled for this formation to date. According to the data of the US Department of Energy (EIA), the initial recoverable reserves

of the Eagle Ford formation amount to 3.37 BBbl of liquid hydrocarbons and 50.2 TCF of gas. According to the EIA, peak oil production in the Eagle Ford formation was reached in 2016 at 1.6 MMbpd and peak gas production was reached in 2015 at 6 BCF. Currently, the development of the Eagle Ford formation covers 24 Texas counties [1]. The rocks are represented by dense limestones (calcite content 45-55%), mudstones and quartz (Fig. 7). In terms of mineralogical and petrographic composition, Eagle Ford shales are similar to rocks of the Pimienta formation, represented by an alternation of tight reservoirs - dense clay limestones and clay shales with a high content of organic carbon (TOC) (Fig. 7) [1]

Fig. 7. Pimienta u Eagle Ford formations mineralogical composition [2, 4].

The Eagle Ford shale formation has been well studied by drilling and it is a clay-carbonate shale. The rocks are represented by dense limestones (calcite content 45-55%), mudstones, and quartz (Fig. 7). The Pimienta formation is confined to the Tithonian stage of the Upper Jurassic, and is similar in mineralogical and petrographic composition to the Eagle Ford shales. The Pimienta formation is an alternation of tight reservoirs - dense clayey limestones and clay shales with a high content of TOC (Fig. 5).

The sedimentation of the Pimienta formation, as well as the Eagle Ford formation, occurred in the conditions of the shelf continental margin, and for this reason their dynamic characteristics of the Eagle Ford and Pimienta formations are similar: with equal permeability - 0.001 mD, the porosity of the Pimienta formation varies from 1.5 to 10%, for Eagle Ford - 4-15%. The reservoir filtration properties are provided by the rocks fracturing. The TOC for the Pimienta formation varies

from 2 to 8%, which is a little bit lower than in the Eagle Ford formation (2-11%). The maximum values of TOC in the Pimienta formation occur in its lower part, starting from depths of 2,900 m or more (Fig. 8), as well

as in the underlying Taman formation, which is an additional source of hydrocarbon with a lower shale potential (Table 1)

Table 1.

Comparative analysis of filtration properties, HC-generation potential, and mineralogical composition of the Pimienta and Eagle Ford formations.

<i>Характеристики</i>	<i>Eagle Ford</i>	<i>Pimienta</i>
Age	U. Cretaceous	U. Jurassic
Depth, м	1500-4300	2200-3500
Gross thickness, м	15-110	40-200
Poro, %	4-15	1.5-10
Permability, mD	0,001	0.001
Quartz, %	20	19
Carbonates, %	45	55
Clay, %	20	15
Pirite, %	3	1
TOC (%)	2.0-11	2-8
Vitrinite, %Ro	0.5-2	0.85-1.7
Reservoir pressure	AHRP	AHRP
Kerogen type	2	2
H2 index, мг/г Cорг	650	600
Sulfur content, %	low	0.1-3
EUR per oil well, MBOE	254-600	-

The productivity of the Pimienta formation has not been sufficiently studied: in the Tampico province, only 25 wells have been drilled, of which only five have been completed horizontally with multi-stage fracturing. The flow rates of light oil range from 278 to 1932

bpd. Similar actual initial flow rates have been obtained for wells in the Eagle Ford formation in Texas, where they range from 14-32 MMCF/d for gas, from 350 to 2,800 bpd for condensate, and from 200 to 950 bpd for oil.

Рис. 8. Фото керн сланцевых формаций Pimienta и Eagle Ford [2, 4].

The inflows are caused by multi-stage fracturing (10-25 stages, 50-100 m each) at the horizontal wells (1200-2500 m). The average value of EUR per well in the oil zone is 350 MBOE. The average "life span" of wells is very small - the drop in oil and gas production reaches 60-80% already in the first year of well operation. Therefore, in order to maintain production at a stable level, it is necessary to constantly drill new wells, which increases the total CAPEX. And the most optimal approach to the development and exploitation of shale HC deposits is the cyclic development [1-5], the essence of which is as follows: after reservoir pressure drops and flow rates decrease to a minimum, wells must be preserved for a sufficient time to restore formation pressure. After pressure is restored due to HC generation processes, the well is put back into production with

almost initial production. Thus, to restore the initial oil flow rate, it is necessary to stop the well for 1-2 months. This method of development can be described as $(36+2)*N$ (where 36 is the months of operation and 2 is the months of well shutdown, N is the number of cycles of replenishment of hydrocarbon deposits depending on the content of TOC, calculated by the potential balance method).

Within Tampico province, taking into account the HC hypercatagenesis in the Pimienta formation, the restoration of the initial HC production can be achieved many times faster than in the case of "normal" catagenesis and well shutdowns can be limited to 1-3 weeks (Fig. 9).

Fig. 9. The principle of cyclic shale development (V.A. Bochkarev [2, 5, 6]).

Currently, there is already evidence of the proposed methodological approach to the development of HC shale deposits. EOG Resources (one of the leading companies developing unconventional HC reserves in the USA) has conducted research on reservoir pressure recovery in wells drilled into the Eagle Ford shale formation. In historical **vertical** wells, repeated fracturing was carried out after 15 years of production. As a result, the well flow rate increased relative to the current one.

Thus, it was possible to keep the well flow rate at an economically efficient level for several years (Fig. 10). At the same time, the wells were stopped only for the period of fracturing, that is, no more than 5-7 days. So during the development process, cracks collapsed and only the near zone in the well worked, while in the remote zone (>5 m) the process of HC generation was "started up" again [3].

Fig. 10 – A graph describing the results obtained by EOG. Recovery of well flow rates during periodic development and fracking (Malanichev A.G., 2018) [2, 4].

Fig 11. The schematic diagram of the cyclic shale development.

From the very beginning of the shale field development, it is necessary to ensure periodic geo-fluid dynamic monitoring and temporary production shutdowns in order to ensure the restoration of HC reserves by resuming the HC generation process. Each new development cycle should begin with repeated fracking to open remote fractures (Fig 11).

The proposed principle of cyclic shale development will significantly minimize the cost of drilling a large number of production wells, extend the life (operation) of existing wells and reduce the CAPEX in general. This approach allows to preserve the generation potential of the developed formations, provides the compliance with the critical depression threshold (about 5 MPa), the implementation of rehabilitation periods ("refueling" for 1-3 weeks for Pimienta formation) and gentle methods of increasing oil and gas

recovery due to the independent restoration of the natural system.

The use of cyclic development of shale hydrocarbons of the Pimienta formation will significantly minimize the cost of drilling a large number of production wells, prolong the life (operation) of already drilled wells and reduce the CAPEX in general [2, 5, 6].

Taking into account the high content of TOC and hypercatagenesis in the Pimienta formation in Tampico province, 3-5 cycles of HC reserves restoration can be expected, which makes this formation one of the most prospective in the world.

Economy. The cost of production of shale oil, natural gas, and condensate has now approached the level of fields with traditional reservoirs, outstripping heavy oil fields and deep water projects. The upper level of

profitability of oil prices for the US market in 2025 is around 28 \$/BBL.

The greater gross thicknesses of the Pimienta formation than Eagle Ford (by 2 times) and the use of cyclic development for the Pimienta formation with repeated fracturing in existing wells will allow for greater accumulated production per well than for wells in the United States, and thereby reduce drilling of additional wells, significantly improving the economic performance of the development shale fields in Mexico.

The launch of exploration of the Pimienta shale formation in 2026 will allow to start development in

2028 and by 2030 to produce an additional 0.4-1.3 MMbpd (Fig. 12) of oil, and by 2040-2050 to reach a production level of about 0.8-2.1 MMbpd, which may fully cover the country's daily oil consumption, and will fully ensure Mexico's energy independence in the future (taking into account the implementation of cyclical shale development) at current consumption levels in the country. Starting in 2032, Mexico will be able to export a surplus of oil to the United States and Central and South American countries.

Fig. 12. Forecast of oil production in Mexico until 2050 due to the shale development of the Pimienta formation, starting in 2028 (by EIA, CNH u CONACYT and author's forecast).

Environmental consequences of the development of the Pimienta formation. Until recently, there was an unofficial ban at the Mexican government on fracking and large-scale fracking at the Pimienta formation. This ban was based mainly on environmental data from the early years of the development of shale formations in the United States, when there were serious environmental problems associated with massive fracking.

The analysis of the environmental situation related to the development of shale formations in the United States and other regions of the world conducted in [2, 5] has shown that modern advanced technologies, together with the increase in oil and gas prices over the past few years, provide opportunities for both economically profitable as well as the environmentally safe extraction of shale HC:

- The use of directional fracking to prevent cracks from bursting into the above-lying water-resistant horizons.
- Reduction of the toxicity of the fracking fluid.
- Purification and reuse of water for fracking.
- Construction of a seawater treatment plant for shale formations geographically located near the Gulf of Mexico

- Active environmental monitoring of artesian and surface waters, soil, and air.

- Analysis of the impact of massive fracking on changes in the seismic activity of the shale formation area using not only traditional methods, but also tracer studies.

- The use of cyclic shale development will significantly reduce the number of production wells, reducing the environmental burden in general.

The Pimienta mega social project. The implementation of shale projects in the state of Tampico and Veracruz will create tens of thousands of jobs. Small towns like Poza Rica will become the operational oil production centers. The city of Veracruz may become the huge shale hub of Mexico, with offices of the world's oil companies and a new oil refining plant for shale oil volumes. Also, to ensure the volume of water for fracking, a water treatment plant can be built to replenish the balance of fresh water according to the principle - for 1 liter of water for fracking – 2 liters of purified water. In addition to major social projects, numerous environmental projects will be implemented, for which there is currently no budget.

Conclusions:

The oil and gas saturated clay-carbonate deposits of the Pimienta formation are both a HC source rock, reservoir and caprock. The HC donor in Pimienta shales is syngenetic organic matter (TOC average - 3.5%), mainly of the sapropel type.

The Eagle Ford formation is a good analogue for the geological study of the Pimienta formation at an early stage of development.

The average EUR values for the Pimienta formation can be about 500 MBBbl of oil per well.

Taking into account the high content of TOC and hypercatagenesis in the Pimienta formation in Tampico province, 3-5 cycles of HC reserves restoration can be expected, which makes this formation one of the most prospective in the world.

The use of cyclic development of shale hydrocarbons of the Pimienta formation will significantly minimize the cost of drilling a large number of production wells, prolong the life (operation) of already drilled wells and reduce the CAPEX in general.

The launch of exploration of the Pimienta shale formation in 2026 will allow to start development in 2028 and by 2030 to produce an additional 0.4-1.3 MMbpd (Fig. 12) of oil, and by 2040-2050 to reach a production level of about 0.8-2.1 MMbpd, which may fully cover the country's daily oil consumption, and will fully ensure Mexico's energy independence in the future (taking into account the implementation of cyclical shale development) at current consumption levels in the country.

Given the location of the Pimienta formation in the condensate and light oil formation zones, gas production (dry and associated) may reach 1-3 BCF/d by 2030 and, together with the shale gas development project extending to Mexico from the Eagle Ford/Agua Nueva formation [6], which will ensure Mexico's gas independence by 2035 and for the long term.

The implementation of shale projects in the state of Tampico and Veracruz will create tens of thousands of jobs and will allow the implementation of many social and environmental projects for which the state budget is currently insufficient.

The main role of Mexican government agencies for the successful implementation of shale projects in Tampico and Veracruz is to ensure a competitive environment and the free participation of drilling companies to reduce well drilling and completion costs to \$5-8 MM\$/well.

Since 2032, Mexico will be able to export a surplus of oil to the United States and Central and South American countries.

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